

ABSTRACT

Staging the Challenge of Ethnic Visibility in British Media

Ethnic diversity in politics and public life, the latest report issued by the House of Commons Library based on Annual Population Survey data finds ‘approximately 16% of the UK population identified with an ethnic group other than White in 2022/23’ (Uberoi & Carthew, 2023:9), a percentage which is supposed to rise up to 30 % by 2050. If these figures suggest that Britain is becoming a more inclusive society, the visibility of ethnic hyphenated Britons in mainstream media is still put to the test. Are these ethnic *others* given fair access to and proportionate representation in the sphere of public expression? Our paper aims to show that even though the representation of BAME (Black, Asian and minority ethnic) citizens in British politics and public life has slowly, but steadily improved since the historic election of 4 non-white MPs in 1987 – Diane Abbott, Paul Boateng, Bernie Grant and Keith Vaz –, their visibility and agency in the media remain challenged by systemic and structural prejudice.

To prove the point, our cross-disciplinary study will focus on the construction of “narratives which stigmatise and further the oppression of minority communities” (Mahmood, 2021). In so doing, we hope to clarify the political stakes involved in “achieving media diversity” (Henry & Olusoga, 2020). But we also need to probe the depth of the ingrained race/class complex that challenges their visibility, just as much as as the ideological/historical hurdles that maintain glass ceilings. Conceived as some kind of socio-political performative script for measuring the degree of belonging, the staging of such narratives is purported to shed the light on how conscious or subconscious bias influences the perception of minorities’ as threats, and deters their entitlement to wider visibility and participation in decision-making with regard to media content production or management.

[294 words]

BIOGRAPHICAL NOTICE

Frédéric Lefrançois is Associate Professor at the Université des Antilles. His current research interests encompass belonging issues in connection with diasporic and national identities. This is why he investigates complementary fields of research dealing with national and cultural identity in the arts of the Americas, Afro-Diasporic Britain, and the Commonwealth Caribbean. His approach, which is interdisciplinary, often confronts representational data with investigation techniques borrowed from Psychoanalysis and Cultural Studies. He has published one monograph, *L’Autre scène du Désir: Strange Fruit de Caryl Phillips*, edited a volume on whiteness in Caribbean painting, *Trinité de Stan Musquer*, translated a book on aesthetics into English, *The Manifesto of Modern Maroonism*, and written multiple contributions to journals and collections of essays.